

A kinetic study of Ru^{III} catalyzed oxidation of galactose and cyclopentanol by potassium bromate in alkaline medium

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Abstract : The kinetics of Ru^{III} catalyzed oxidation of D(+)-galactose (galac) and cyclopentanol (cyclopen) by KBrO₃ in alkaline medium using mercuric acetate as a scavenger for Br⁻ ion (galac) as well as co-catalyst (cyclopen), have been studied in the temperature range 30–45 °C. The reactions exhibit first-order kinetics with respect to oxidant and catalyst while zero-order kinetics with respect to substrate was observed in case of both galactose and cyclopentanol. For cyclopentanol, a positive effect on the rate of reaction were observed on successive addition of [Hg(OAc)₂] and [Cl⁻] whereas [OH⁻] exhibited an inverse fractional order. In case of galactose, [OH⁻] and [Hg(OAc)₂] have no effect on the reaction velocity. A positive fractional order in acetic acid concentration (AcOH) and negligible effect of ionic strength of the medium were observed.

The reactive species of Ru^{III} in alkaline medium is [RuCl₂(H₂O)₃(OH)] (galac) and [RuCl₃(H₂O)₂OH]⁻¹ (cyclopen) under the experimental pH range. A suitable mechanism in conformity with the kinetic observation has been proposed. The various activation parameters such as energy of activation (ΔE*), Arrhenius factor (A), entropy of activation (ΔS*) were calculated from the rate measurements at 30, 35, 40 and 45 °C. A rate law has been derived on the basis of data obtained.

Keywords : Ru^{III}, galactose, cyclopentanol, oxidation, kinetics.

Introduction

Oxidants like sodium periodate^{1,2}, *N*-bromoacetamide^{3,4}, *N*-bromosuccinimide^{5,6} etc. have been earlier used in oxidation of various compounds in presence of catalyst. Potassium bromate has been used as an oxidant in various catalyzed reactions^{7,8}. The use of Ru^{III} chloride as a catalyst has been reported by several workers in acidic medium. But little work has been reported on Ru^{III} catalyzed oxidation by potassium bromate in alkaline medium. This prompted us to undertake the present investigation of the kinetic study of Ru^{III} catalyzed oxidation of cyclopentanol and galactose by potassium bromate in alkaline medium with mercuric acetate as a scavenger.

Experimental

Materials : Aqueous solution of galactose and cyclopentanol (E. Merck), potassium bromate (B.D.H., A.R.), NaClO₄ and Hg(OAc)₂ (E. Merck) were prepared by dissolving the weighed amount of sample in triple distilled water. NaOH (S.D. fine) was used as a source of

OH⁻ ions. Ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson Matthey) was prepared by dissolving the sample in HCl of known strength. The reaction stills were painted black so as to prevent photochemical effects.

Kinetics : A thermostated waterbath was used to maintain the desired temperature within ±0.1 °C. Requisite volume of reagents including substrate, were taken in a reaction vessel and thermostated at 35 ±0.1 °C for thermal equilibrium. A measured volume of KBrO₃ solution, which was also maintained separately at the same temperature, was rapidly poured into the reaction vessel. The kinetics was followed by examining desired portions of reaction mixture for KBrO₃ iodometrically using starch as an indicator after suitable time intervals.

Results and discussion

The stoichiometric analysis of the oxidation of galactose and cyclopentanol with potassium bromate indicates that one mole of oxidant reacts with one mole of substrate. Thus, over all reaction may be represented as :

From the above equation, it is clear that galactonic acid and cyclopentanone (for galac and cyclophen respectively) were identified as main products.

(i) Cyclopentanone was identified by TLC and also through dinitrophenyl hydrazine (DNP) derivative as follows :

1 ml of reaction mixture in dilute HCl was added to 3 ml of the 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine solution and shaken well. A yellowish precipitate was formed which was the hydrazone according to the following equation.

The derivative was dried and its melting point was determined. The recorded melting point of DNP derivative of cyclopentanone is 145 °C (actual melting point 146 °C).

(ii) Galactonic acid was identified by the following method :

Few milligrams of unknown compound was added to 1 ml of 5% sodium bicarbonate solution. Evolution of carbon dioxide with effervescence indicated the presence of acidic group in the given compound.

The effect of an increase in substrate concentration on the reaction rate indicated zero-order reaction with respect to galactose and cyclopentanol.

It was observed that the value of k_1 (i.e $-dc/dt/[\text{KBrO}_3]$) were constant at all initial concentrations of KBrO_3 , show-

Fig. 1. Plot between $[\text{KBrO}_3]$ and $(-dc/dt)$ for oxidation of D(+)-galactose (A) and cyclopentanol (B) at 35 °C.

ing first-order dependence on $[\text{KBrO}_3]$ (Fig. 1). First-order dependence on $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ is evident from the close resemblance between the slopes $1.09 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (for galac) and $6.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $12.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (for cyclophen) at 35 °C and 45 °C respectively of $(-dc/dt)$ vs $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ plots (Fig. 2) and the average values of experimental k_1 values $1.03 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $1.96 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (for galactose) and $7.15 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $13.7 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (for cyclopent) at 35 °C and 45 °C respectively.

Fig. 2. Plot between $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ and $(-dc/dt)$ for oxidation of D(+)-galactose (A) and cyclopentanol (B) at 35 °C (A) (B) and 45 °C (A') (B') respectively.

In the case of galactose, variation in ionic strength of the medium, $[\text{OH}^-]$ and [mercuric acetate] show negligible effect on the reaction rate. The negligible effect of mercuric acetate excludes the possibility of its involvement either as a catalyst or as an oxidant because it does not help the reaction to proceed without bromate. Hence the role of mercuric acetate here is as a scavenger⁹⁻¹¹ for any bromide ion formed in the reaction and it helps to eliminate the parallel oxidation by Br_2 which would have

been formed as a result of interaction between Br^- ion and BrO_3^- ion.

Kinetic results obtained on varying chloride ion concentration show positive effect, which means the rate of reaction increases with increase in $[\text{Cl}^-]$ (in case of cyclophen) while decreases (in galac), as seen in Table 1. In case of cyclopentanol, a positive effect on the rate of reaction were observed. The rate measurements were taken at 30–45 °C and specific rate constants were used to

Table 1. Effect of variation of reactants on the reaction rate at 35 °C : $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 2.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$, $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$

[Substrate] $\times 10^2 \text{ M}$	[NaOH] $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$	[KCl] $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$	[Hg(OAc) ₂] $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$	[NaClO ₄] $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$	$(-dc/dt) \times 10^7 \text{ M L}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	
					Galactose	Cyclopentanol
0.33	1.00	1.00	1.25	-	2.20	1.30
0.40	1.00	1.00	1.25	-	2.14	1.28
0.50	1.00	1.00	1.25	-	2.33	1.54
0.66	1.00	1.00	1.25	-	2.50	1.62
1.00	1.00	1.00	1.25	-	2.33	1.38
2.00	1.00	1.00	1.25	-	2.50	1.60
2.00	0.83	1.00	1.25	-	2.22	2.02
2.00	1.00	1.00	1.25	-	2.50	1.60
2.00	1.25	1.00	1.25	-	2.25	1.42
2.00	1.67	1.00	1.25	-	2.33	1.20
2.00	2.50	1.00	1.25	-	2.80	0.98
2.00	5.00	1.00	1.25	-	2.18	0.66
2.00	1.00	0.83	1.25	-	3.35	1.33
2.00	1.00	1.00	1.25	-	2.50	1.60
2.00	1.00	1.25	1.25	-	2.25	2.00
2.00	1.00	1.67	1.25	-	1.85	2.34
2.00	1.00	2.50	1.25	-	1.62	2.68
2.00	1.00	5.00	1.25	-	1.20	2.98
2.00	1.00	1.00	0.83	-	2.42	0.92
2.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	-	2.23	1.24
2.00	1.00	1.00	1.25	-	2.50	1.60
2.00	1.00	1.00	1.67	-	2.22	1.98
2.00	1.00	1.00	2.50	-	2.33	2.82
2.00	1.00	1.00	5.00	-	2.40	3.86
2.00	1.00	1.00	1.25	0.83	2.25	1.74
2.00	1.00	1.00	1.25	1.00	2.22	1.60
2.00	1.00	1.00	1.25	1.25	2.33	1.58
2.00	1.00	1.00	1.25	1.67	2.33	1.46
2.00	1.00	1.00	1.25	2.50	2.20	1.72
2.00	1.00	1.00	1.25	5.00	2.25	1.64

Fig. 3. Plot between $1/T \times 10^4$ and $4 + \log k$ for oxidation of D(+)-galactose (A) and cyclopentanol (B) at 35 °C.

draw a plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ which was linear (Fig. 3).

The values of activation energy (ΔE^*), Arrhenius factor (A), entropy of activation (ΔS^*) and free energy of activation (ΔG^*) were calculated from the rate measurement at 30, 35, 40 and 45 °C respectively, which have been recorded in Table 2.

Table 2. Activation parameters for alkaline bromate oxidation of galactose and cyclopentanol at different temperature

Parameters	Temp. (°C)	Galactose	Cyclopentanol
$k_r \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)	30	1.82	1.12
$k_r \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)	35	2.50	1.60
$k_r \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)	40	3.58	2.34
$k_r \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)	45	4.96	3.18
ΔE^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-	60.92	54.71
$\log A$	35	10.72	9.48
ΔS^*	35	-10.37	-16.05
ΔG^*	35	74.34	75.48
ΔH^*	-	71.14	70.53

$[\text{KBrO}_3] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2] = 1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{KCl}] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$.

$[\text{Substrate}] = 2.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 2.40 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$.

Ru^{III} chloride has been reported to give a number of possible chloro species dependent on pH of the solution, Ru^{III} exists in the following equilibrium under the ex-

perimental pH range 10–12¹².

The following reaction steps are suggested on the basis of above discussion for oxidation of galactose and cyclopentanol by bromate in presence of ruthenium(III) chloride as a catalyst in alkaline medium.

S = Galactose

Mechanism for oxidation of galactose

where [S] = cyclopentanol and [P] = cyclopentanone

Mechanism for oxidation of cyclopentanol

Now considering the above steps and applying the steady state treatment with a reasonable approximation, the rate law derived as follows :

$$\frac{-d[\text{BrO}_3^-]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{BrO}_3^-]}{[\text{Cl}^-] + K_1} \quad (\text{for galactose})$$

$$\frac{-d[\text{BrO}_3^-]}{dt} = \frac{K_2 K_3 [\text{Cl}^-] [\text{Hg}^{2+}] [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{BrO}_3^-]}{[\text{OH}^-] (K_1 + [\text{Cl}^-]) + (K_2 [\text{Cl}^-]) (1 + K_3 [\text{Hg}^{2+}])}$$

(for cyclopentanol)

where $K_1 = k_1/k_{-1}$, $K_2 = k_2/k_{-2}$, $K_3 = k_3/k_{-3}$.

The rate law is in agreement with all observed kinetics. The proposed mechanism is in consistent with the activation parameters given in Table 2.

Conclusion :

The experimental results reveal that the reaction rate was doubled, when concentration of the catalyst Ru^{III} is doubled. The rate law equation is in conformity with all kinetic observations and the proposed mechanistic steps are supported by the negligible effect of ionic strength. Positive effect of AcOH signifies a negative dielectric effect. The high positive values of free energy of activation (ΔG^*) indicates highly solvated transition state, while fairly high negative values of entropy of activation (ΔS^*) suggest the formation of an activated complex with reduction in degree of freedom. From the present investigation it is concluded that BrO_3^- and $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3\text{OH}]$ (galac) and $[\text{RuCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{OH}]^-$ (cyclopen) are reactive species obtained from KBrO_3 and ruthenium(III) chloride respectively in alkaline medium.

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